

*(Pruchnicki M. (2022). [Ukrainian children are fleeing Russian aggression. Przemyśl, Poland 27/02/2022]
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PLANS AND REFLECTIONS ON THE INTEGRATION OF UKRAINIAN REFUGEES IN BASEL

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April 2023

This paper was written as a part of the OFB project grants 2022

**Osteuropa
Forum
Basel**

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The research can be downloaded here <https://ukrainianrefugeesinbasel.wordpress.com/>

INTRODUCTION

The Ukrainian refugee crisis started as a result of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on February 24th, 2022. As of February 6th, 2023, there are more than four million Ukrainian refugees (registered for temporary protection) in Europe, 78'888 of them in Switzerland (UNHCR, 2023). While Switzerland is not among the top countries, where Ukrainian refugees go in absolute numbers, it is still an important destination given the size of the country. Together with Austria, Belgium, and Netherlands, Switzerland is a place of temporary protection for less than 100'000 Ukrainians in each country (UNHCR, 2023).

Ukrainian refugees settled in all of the 26 Swiss cantons. According to the data, as of January 31st, 2023, there are 1'850 Ukrainian refugees in the Canton of Basel-City.

As the war in Ukraine continues and the number of refugees in Switzerland rises, the question of further planning and integrating of refugees becomes more relevant. Therefore, this study **aims** at defining the reflections on the integration and future plans of Ukrainian refugees in Basel.

The **research questions**, which drive this study are:

- 1) What are the plans of Ukrainian refugees in Basel for the near future (till 2024)?
- 2) What are the reflections on the integration of Ukrainian refugees in Basel?

Knowing the answers to these questions is of utmost importance both for the Federal and Cantonal authorities as well as for the general public, because they can inform further target measures to be taken to facilitate integration and improve living conditions.

Overall, these questions examine the issue from two perspectives. The first research question is dedicated to the **people's agency**, which is the capacity of the Ukrainians to express their will and to act accordingly. Despite being refugees, Ukrainians have subjectivity and can influence their lives by making future plans.

The second one explores the structural dimension, which is reflected through the domains of integration (rights, employment, education, etc).

The **object** of research is Ukrainian refugees in Basel, more precisely this category includes women from 18 to 60 years old, who received the "S" status in the canton of Basel-City.

The theoretical framework of this research is based on the concept of successful refugee integration created by Ager and Strang (Ager & Strang, 2008), which will be discussed in more detail below.

The empirical part of this exploratory, qualitative research was conducted in Basel in 2022-2023 and consists of ten anonymous in-depth semi-structured interviews taken online and offline in Ukrainian.

BACKGROUND

On February 24th, 2022 Russia started the invasion of Ukraine, which caused a new wave of refugees in Europe, the fastest-growing refugee crisis since WWII. As a result, millions of people fled Ukraine: according to the official data, on January 31st, 2023, there are 4'823'326 Ukrainian refugees registered for Temporary Protection or similar national protection schemes in Europe (UNHCR, 2023).

As a reaction to the crisis, in March 2022, the EU Parliament adopted the Temporary Protection Directive for people fleeing the war in Ukraine. This directive allows people to benefit from the same rights across the EU (resident permit, the possibility to work, access to medical assistance, access to social welfare, and keeping Ukrainian driving licenses in the EU) (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022).

Despite not being a part of the EU, Switzerland implemented a similar scheme. In March 2022, the Swiss Federal Council confirmed the implementation of the so-called status "S" following the Temporary Protection activated by the European Parliament (Swiss Federal Council, 2022). Thus, in Switzerland, Ukrainian refugees are eligible to hold "S" status, which has never been granted before to any other group of people seeking protection in Switzerland. In comparison to the "B" or "F" permit, people with an "S" permit are recognized as vulnerable persons but not as refugees. They are granted temporary residence in Switzerland.

Holders of this status are eligible to work in Switzerland, receive social and health services, get an education, and travel outside Switzerland (with some limitations). At first, the "S" permit was temporarily granted for the period of one year but on November 9th, 2022, the Federal Council decided to lift the protection status "S" for Ukrainian refugees before March 4th, 2024 (The Federal Council, 2022).

In terms of the predictions of the number of Ukrainian refugees in Switzerland, the experts

of the State Secretariat for Migration estimated that by the end of 2022, 85'000 - 120'000 Ukrainian refugees would be in Switzerland (State Secretariat for Migration, 2022b). But updated figures in February 2023 showed that there are only 78'888 refugees from Ukraine in Switzerland (UNHCR, 2023).

In this context, it is important to stress that the Ukrainian refugee crisis has some features, which make it unique among previous refugee crises in Europe. Firstly, 90% of the refugees fleeing Ukraine are women and children (UNHCR, 2022a). According to the law, most men from 18 to 60 are not allowed to cross the Ukrainian border and leave Ukraine (Law No. 3857-XII, 1994). But those men, who: 1) raise three or more children under the age of 18; 2) have a certificate of deferment of conscription and notification of enrollment in special military registration; 3) are engaged in the constant care for persons in need, etc are eligible to cross the border. Secondly, Ukrainian refugees are treated differently in Europe. Europeans feel closer to Ukrainians than to other refugees “because of their similar ethnic and religious backgrounds, the shared conscience collective, and the European public’s cultural proximity to Ukraine” (De Coninck, 2022). Thirdly, the EU Temporary Protection Directive (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022) was implemented for Ukrainian refugees, which is the first of its kind in the history of the European Union.

STATE OF ART: REFUGEES AND THEIR INTEGRATION WITHIN THE FORCED MIGRATION

Refugees have always been a research interest of sociologists (Castles, 2003; Zetter, 2007). While conducting research in the field of migration and particularly in the field of forced migration, it is important to distinguish between the concepts of “refugees” and “migrants”.

According to the 1951 Refugee Convention, a refugee is “someone unable or unwilling to return to their country of origin owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion” (UN General Assembly, 1951). The concept of “migrant” lacks the formal definition, but most researchers agree that it can be defined as “someone who changes his or her country of usual residence, irrespective of the reason for migration or legal status” (International Organization for Migration, 2019).

In terms of the Ukrainian refugee crisis, Ukrainians have the legal status of temporary

protection seekers (not refugees) in countries of the European Union and Switzerland although they are usually labeled as “Ukrainian refugees”.

The experience of fleeing and refugees is the object of forced migration, which must be researched within migration studies (FitzGerald & Arar, 2018, p. 400). It must be stressed that currently displacement is understood as a phenomenon, which affects all sides, including the refugees themselves, the host communities, governments, and international organizations (Colson, 2003).

Therefore, Stephen Castles states that forced migration should be researched because it is a central aspect of social transformation in the contemporary world (Castles, 2003, p. 14). Discussing the work in the field, Richard Black pointed out that the period during 1980-2000 was dedicated to the increase in academic research and institutional work in the branch (Black, 2001), whereas the period of 2015-2021 focused mainly on the work connected with the refugees from Syria (Ociepa-Kicińska & Gorzałczyńska-Koczkodaj, 2022).

Within the field, one of the central concepts is the integration of forcibly displaced people in the host communities. Integration becomes a crucial question for all involved ones, especially in forced migration policy (Philip & Berthon, 2023).

The biggest part of the study on the integration of refugees includes practical studies on the cases in particular countries. They aim at encircling the problem, collecting and observing data, defining challenges, and usage of data and conclusions in the policy-making process.

Although there are different and even multimethod approaches (Mijić & Parzer, 2022) to the refugees’ integration, the UN Refugee Agency defines integration as “multi-dimensional in that it relates both to the conditions for and actual participation in all aspects of the economic, social, cultural, civil and political life of the country of resettlement as well as to refugees’ own perceptions of, acceptance by and membership in the host society” (UNHCR, 2002). This definition is similar to the one by Ager and Strang, in which they stress that integration is “a multidimensional process, which should be searched through ten core domains” (Ager & Strang, 2008, p. 167). These domains include employment, housing, education, health, social bonds, social links, social bridges, language and cultural knowledge, safety and stability, rights, and citizenship.

In terms of these domains, according to the report made by The UN Refugee Agency, employment, and language acquisition are crucial for refugee integration (UNHCR, 2013).

Adding to the key components of the integration, research from Switzerland on Syrian

refugees indicates that the practical problems within the integration process are closely connected to psychological (emotional) ones (Kiselev et al., 2020).

As the Ukrainian refugee crisis started a year ago, in 2022, there exists a lack of research on the integration of Ukrainian refugees in Europe and Switzerland. Most current studies are conducted in the quantitative framework, which aims at monitoring the forced migration flows (UNHCR, 2022b) and predicting the scale of the crisis (Dadush & Weil, 2022).

In the countries of the European Union, there are some studies on the prospects of integration of Ukrainian refugees (Panchenko, 2022), (Duszczuk & Kaczmarczyk, 2022). Currently, in Switzerland, there is data on Ukrainian refugees, collected by SEM, and a small number of surveys, which mostly focus on the Russo-Ukrainian war and its consequences (Atteslander et al., 2022).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This exploratory and qualitative research is informed by the theoretical framework of refugee integration created by Ager & Strang in “Understanding integration: a conceptual framework” (2008).

This theoretical framework aims at indicating the central elements of “successful integration”. The authors state that there are some main domains (employment, housing, education, health, social bonds, social links, social bridges, language, and cultural knowledge, safety, stability, rights and citizenship), through which the concept of integration can be analysed.

According to the authors, the fundamental domain is “Rights and Citizenships”, which can be searched through the rules and practices in this field. The domains “Language and Cultural Knowledge” and “Safety and Stability” are the facilitators of successful integration. The social connection can be described through three main domains “Social bridges” (the connection between the groups of refugees and host communities), “Social bonds” (the connection between the members of the refugee groups), and “Social links” (the connection between refugees and the structures of the state, such as government services). And the last four domains “Employment”, “Housing”, “Education”, and “Health” belong to the Markers and Means.

METHODOLOGY

Respondents of the study

Ten respondents were interviewed for the study. The respondents are women, aged 18-60, who are “S” status holders in Canton of Basel-City. The criteria for sampling are as follows: Firstly, mainly women and children (up to 18 years old) are eligible to cross the Ukrainian border. Secondly, the sample includes only those people, who are eligible to work and do not get a pension. In Ukraine, the age group of 18-60-year-old women can work legally (Law No. 1058-IV, 2003). Thirdly, as the research is about the refugees in the Canton of Basel-City, the respondents are considered to be “S” status holders in the Canton of Basel-City. In this study, non-probability snowball sampling was adopted, in which respondents helped recruit other respondents by sharing their contacts with the interviewer.

Most of the respondents have never been to Basel before and do not have any friends or relatives in Basel and in general in Switzerland. Some of the women arrived with the members of their nuclear family (children, parents, husbands), and some of them arrived without any family members. Overall, the study population is diverse in terms of age, occupation, and marital status.

Data collection

This study is conducted within the qualitative research framework. It is based on the method of semi-structured interviews (Knott et al., 2022).

The respondents were recruited through groups of Ukrainian refugees on Telegram, Facebook, and the researcher’s networks. Sharing the call for participation in the research was not an effective tool for recruiting the respondents. Therefore, the refugees were contacted by private messages with a proposal to participate in the interviews and share their personal experiences.

The interviews were conducted from November 2022 to February 2023. All interviews were conducted after publishing the information that the status “S” in Switzerland will be valid until 2024.

Four face-to-face interviews were offline and six interviews were online via Zoom, Viber calls and Messenger calls. The duration of each interview was around 40 - 60 minutes.

The researcher, who was the interviewer, is herself a Ukrainian citizen and “S” status holder in the Canton of Ticino, who can speak both Ukrainian and Russian. Based on these

factors, the researcher was easily welcomed in the refugee community. Because of the similar experience and the opportunity to express their ideas in their mother tongue, the respondents were more open and sincere during the interviews.

At the beginning of the interviews, the researcher gave oral information about the study and details about privacy (anonymous interviews and secure storing of the data). Participation in the interviews was completely voluntary. Informed consent was given orally. The interviewer informed the respondents that they could choose the language of the interview between Russian and Ukrainian. Overall, 10 interviews were conducted in Ukrainian.

The interview guide reflects the theoretical approach of the study and is designed according to the ten core domains of integration (Ager & Strang, 2008). The respondents were asked questions covering the topics around their integration in Basel: employment, housing, education, health, social connections, language, safety and stability. Besides the reflections on the integration, the guide consists of questions on the experience of fleeing and plans for the near future (till 2024). Overall, the guide consists of five chapters: Chapter 1 “Socio-demographic questions and experience of fleeing”; Chapter 2 “Markers and means of integration (employment, housing, education, health); Chapter 3 “Social connections”; Chapter 4 “Facilitators of the integration (language, safety, and stability); Chapter 5 “Plans for near future”.

Data analysis

All interviews were recorded on a dictaphone and later transferred to text data in Word and then Excel files. After that, the text data were grouped according to the subtopics, which corresponded to the chapter of the guide. The data were analyzed using standard qualitative thematic interpretation using Excel to organize and assist in the process.

In this study, all respondents’ names are pseudonymized randomly.

FINDINGS

These findings correspond to the research questions of this study. The findings are presented according to the thematic groups.

Experience of fleeing

All respondents came to Basel in 2022. While describing the experience of fleeing, they mention two main reasons for coming. Some of them state that they had relatives or friends in Basel and came to them intentionally. But others say that arriving at Basel happened accidentally as the volunteers helping Ukrainians to flee suggested Basel or Switzerland as a possible destination.

Refugees say that the opportunity to be in safety or/and to get their children in safety is the main underlying reason for making the decision to flee.

For example, Anna (40 years old) and Maria (34 years old) describe their experience of fleeing and how the decision was made:

“I had a phone call and volunteers asked me whether I wanted to flee. I had some hours to think about it. I agreed. I have two children. I did not want them to see the war. I did not know where we were going.” (Anna)

Maria, who is a mother of a 7-year-old daughter says:

“We came to Basel a week before the war started because my mom had a birthday. She had been living in Basel for more than ten years because she got married here. When the war started, we decided to stay on.” (Maria)

In general, while describing the experience of fleeing, respondents emphasize the priority of safety. They say that the decision to go abroad was difficult for them. For some respondents, the way to Switzerland was through some intermediate stops in Poland and Germany. Those respondents, who had relatives or friends in Basel, arranged their travel with their help. Those respondents, who arrived in Switzerland accidentally, were helped by different volunteers helping Ukrainians.

Employment

Bearers of the Status “S” card are eligible to work in Switzerland. Respondents express a high interest in employment. Also, they admit that employment is strongly connected with their level of the German language. As for the time of interviewing, they stressed that they were

focusing on improving their language skills by attending language classes and passing the exams to get language proficiency certificates. The courses are organized in Basel as follows: learning German is not mandatory; the courses at language schools are paid for by Canton; people can choose which type of course (general, intensive) they would like to attend.

Despite showing the desire to work, the respondents name some main challenges, which occur within employment.

According to the respondents, *mental health* plays a crucial role. Stress, anxiety, sleep problems, and as a consequence, lack of energy, influences the process of finding a job and integrating into new groups.

For example, Kate (49 years old) describes her health problems and how they influence her life:

“Mentally, I feel very bad. I am often ill and I often visit a psychologist. It is even hard to think about the job now. I do not sleep well. I wake up in the middle of the night. When I feel better mentally, I will think about the job.” (Kate)

Alla (55 years old), who is from Odesa and used to work in the port, comments on her efforts in employment in this way:

“I do not work but I would like to. It is difficult for me to sit without a job. But I need to know the language very well. Where can I work? Switzerland... They are not interested in us as workers. It is very difficult...” (Alla)

The next issue, which influences the possibility of mothers being employed, is taking *care of children*. Women, who have children, admit that children's schedules in preprimary and primary schools and lack of the help of a second parent prevent them from learning a language faster and finding a full-time job.

The schedule of the preprimary and primary education institutions in Basel and the impossibility to share the reproductive labor among the family members become a crucial problem among the mothers.

Olga, who is 35 years old and who has a 7-year-old son comments:

“I want to work. But it is difficult to find a job without speaking German. One more problem is that I need to pick my son up from school every day and help him do homework. And I have to take care of my son by myself. He often gets cold. I need to be with him when he is ill.” (Olga)

Also, respondents are not ready to change the occupation they had in Ukraine and start working in a new sphere. They expressed readiness to spend more time on training and education courses to continue to work in their profession.

For example, Anna, who was an accountant in Ukraine and had two jobs explains her plans for the future:

“Currently I am working in the library for only two hours per week. I can talk to people there and improve my oral skills. It makes me speak only German because there are no Ukrainians there. When I speak German better, I will be given more hours. I want to work as an accountant (the same as in Ukraine). I need to learn the program for accountants in German. I want to do it till summer.” (Anna)

Maria, whose occupation is architecture comments on her employment in Switzerland:

“I am not working now. I feel bad about that. I want to work but most of my time dedicate to studying German. But I am learning general German, not the language for architecture. In Ukraine, I learned our norms and rules in architecture but here I must start everything from the very beginning. Also, I am working on my own project. I am writing a bilingual book in Ukrainian and German and I am creating illustrations for this book. I had the experience of writing children's books in Ukraine.” (Maria)

To sum up, employment is one of the most challenging issues for Ukrainian refugees. They underline that it is strongly connected to the German language proficiency and they are currently putting their efforts into learning the language. Despite mostly expressing the desire to find a job and start working, there are many obstacles that prevent them from a rapid integration into the job market, such as problems with mental health, taking care of children, and changing occupations. As it was stated before, the feature, which makes this crisis special,

is that the majority of the refugees are women, who fled without the fathers of the children. It creates circumstances, where women cannot share the responsibilities and as a consequence, they cannot work full-time.

Housing

In Switzerland, Ukrainian refugees are usually provided housing by Canton. The apartments are rented by the Social Assistance Service (State Secretariat for Migration, 2022a). Most respondents describe the accommodation as comfortable and spacious and add that they do not have any problems with it.

For example, Olena (36 years old), who is a mother of three children and who came to Basel with her husband describes their accommodation in this way:

“We pay for the flat by ourselves, because my husband works. We feel comfortable, despite the fact that we are a big family. We have three spacious rooms and the flat is well-furnished.” (Olena)

But Kate has the opposite experience:

“I live in a flat but the problem is that renting this flat is short-termed. I could not find a flat for a long period of time. And now I need to find a new flat again. I was assigned a room by the Canton, which I could not lock because it did not have a key. But I need a minimum of comfort. If I cannot have a minimum of comfort, it is better for me to come back to Ukraine.” (Kate)

Overall, most respondents do not have problems with the accommodation in Basel and describe it as comfortable and safe.

Education

It is mandatory for children and teenagers to get primary and secondary education in Switzerland (State Secretariat for Migration, 2022a).

Most respondents, whose children go to kindergartens or schools, express their satisfaction with their children's education and socialization processes. Moreover, they claim they want to take some ideas back to Ukrainian schools and kindergartens, like the focus of primary education on soft skills and some teaching approaches.

Maria describes her experience:

“My daughter, who is in the second grade, went to the school when it was the twelfth day of the war. We were invited to school. All children were prepared to meet a new girl from Ukraine. They created postcards, and invitations and even learned some Ukrainian words. I really liked the teacher. She started communicating with my daughter in a very light, supportive, and friendly way. Children started to bring their toys. It was a wave of kindness. It gave me the feeling that everything would be okay. Now the situation is really good. My daughter can say full sentences in German.” (Maria)

Moreover, parents stress the high quality of communication with the administration and describe it as productive and empathetic. Additionally, the mental health of the students and integration became the top priorities for teachers and carers.

According to the respondents, the only problem, which may exist in the future when children may come back to Ukraine, is the inconsistency of school curriculums in Ukraine and Switzerland.

Nadia, who is 48 years old and has two sons, tells about their experience and evaluates the experience as a positive one:

“My two children are in secondary school. School is 100 from 100. They created great conditions for the children. They always ask whether some topics can be traumatizing for children or not. When there was a parent-teacher conference, the Council of Education invited a translator for me to help communicate with the teachers. Teachers love their job and always have good contact with children and parents.” (Nadia)

Overall, respondents with children describe the education institutions in Basel in a positive way mentioning good experience and high quality of provided education services. They say that neither they nor their children do not have any problems with kindergartens

and schools.

Healthcare

In Switzerland, Ukrainian refugees are eligible to get health insurance from the cantonal authorities (State Secretariat for Migration, 2022a).

While describing the experience, respondents mention that in general, they do not have problems with getting medical assistance. In order to overcome language barriers, they use tools such as Google Translator or find Russian or Ukrainian-speaking doctors.

Valentyna, who is 43 years old, describes her experience:

“Google helps a lot. When I received the insurance card, I found the doctor, who was Russian-speaking. It is much better for me. I receive all the services and help that I need.”
(Valentyna)

The challenge, which may occur within the health services, is the difference in treatment approaches in Ukraine and Switzerland. For example, Olga describes her challenging experience:

“My child was ill. We went to the hospital. It was surprising that in comparison to Ukraine, we did not get help immediately because my son had a fever. There were a lot of questions, and questionnaires, long time to wait. In general, I did not like how it worked. It was difficult for me to communicate with doctors.” ***(Olga)***

In general, most respondents stated that they do not have problems with the health services in Basel even despite not having well-developed German-speaking skills. But some respondents mention that the approach to the treatment differs a lot from the one they were getting in Ukraine. For example, in Ukraine, it is common to go to the emergency room or have an immediate doctor's appointment, or call an ambulance, when the child has a fever. But in Switzerland, people usually go to the emergency room only for accidents.

The contrast between expectations and actual experiences results in culture shock, which may be frustrating for the refugees.

Social Connections

Ukrainians in Basel organize different initiatives and projects together. Moreover, they have different groups on Telegram and Facebook, where they communicate and solve problems together.

Maria, whose daughter goes to a Ukrainian school, describes how she communicates with other refugees. She also mentions the language as the reason for making friends:

“I met a lot of Ukrainians in the Ukrainian school “Barvinok”, where my daughter goes. We organize a lot of events, for instance, “Smakolyky”. Everybody is active. Some people organize dancing clubs for children, and some people hold drawing classes. But I have two closest friends here. We are together because all of us speak Ukrainian.” (Maria)

Alla emphasizes that she has a lot of acquaintances in Basel:

“I met a lot of Ukrainians at the church. Sometimes I meet some people even at the bus stops. We keep in touch together, go for a walk. Also, we meet in the places where we can go together with the children.” (Alla)

When Ukrainian refugees started to come to Basel, some Swiss families hosted them. Respondents say that they continue keeping in touch with them. Moreover, respondents stressed that they would like to communicate with the Swiss more.

Valentyna describes her experience of making friends with Swiss people:

“I have some Swiss friends here. They help me a lot. I am very happy that I met such good people. I already know their friends and we keep in touch with them, as well. I met them at the school, where I study German. We keep in touch with our teachers, even sometimes go to the cafe together.” (Valentyna)

Anastasia, who is 30 years old, says:

“I want to communicate more with Swiss people but unfortunately I did not have the

opportunity to meet them.” (Anastasia)

While describing the experience of communication with any sort of governmental institution, most respondents say that they have no negative feedback.

Olga describes her experience:

“Fast and easy. Sometimes it takes time to solve some problems, but I understand that. The translators help a lot. I am very thankful to them”. (Olga)

The social connections of Ukrainian refugees should be searched through the connection with other refugees, host communities, and government agencies. Regarding the connection with government agencies, refugees mention that in general, they do not have problems as social workers are always ready to help to solve the problems.

Refugees continue keeping in touch with the Swiss families, who hosted them and positively describe this experience. Moreover, in general, respondents describe Swiss people as “kind and supportive people”. But one respondent mentioned that she feels supremacy in the attitude of Swiss people to Ukrainian refugees: ***“In Ukraine, I knew that I could find a job, communicate and be equal with other people - I do not feel it here. I have repeatedly encountered the fact that the Swiss put themselves above Ukrainians” (Olga)***

Regarding keeping in touch with other refugees, respondents mention that they have several Ukrainian communities (online and offline), where it is possible to keep in touch with each other. Among offline communities refugees name “Smkolyky”, Ukrainian school “Barvinok”, and churches, where different events for refugees take place. Among online communities, they name groups on Facebook and Telegram.

Some respondents mentioned that they make friends only with those people, who speak Ukrainian.

Language

All respondents learn German and admit how important it is to have a high language proficiency in order to be successful in communication, employment, and integration, in

general. Only one respondent has already had an elementary level of German before fleeing. Some respondents have an intermediate level of English.

Among the factors, which influence the intensity of learning German, respondents mention the method of teaching, help with children, and mental health.

Anastasia describes her experience in this way:

“Learning German is the most difficult issue for me. I love studying but now I do not have the opportunity, because I have a little kid. I started to visit language courses and left my kid at the “room for kids”, but she was very nervous there and caught a virus. So I cannot say that it was a productive education.” (Anastasia)

Some respondents say that some methods of teaching are challenging for them. For example, there exists a problem, when the teacher is monolingual and explains everything in German. The next factor is taking care of children, which does not let them intensively learn a language. And the third issue is stress and anxiety, which prevent learning a new language.

Olena says:

“Yes, I study German. It is obligatory for me. We are in German-speaking Canton, it makes you learn the language if you want to communicate.” (Olena)

Safety and Stability

People generally underline that they feel safe in Basel. But additionally, they mention that they can suffer from anxiety and sadness.

Valentyna, whose son is in Ukraine and who fled with her sister and a nephew says:

“Emotionally, it is difficult because you are alone abroad. There is no feeling that you are at home. I understand that it is temporary and we all hope for the best. It is life and we need to accept it as it is.” (Valentyna)

The general situation in Ukraine has a big influence on their mood. Moreover, the big number of challenges with learning a new language, finding a job, and issues with accommodation may make them feel frustrated.

Victoria, who is 51 years old, says:

“I feel secure and insecure. At first, I felt frustrated, because I left Ukraine. But now I sometimes feel that I am not a well-qualified worker. I often visit a psychologist. I understand that now I need some help and I am not afraid to ask for this help”.
(Victoria)

Future plans and intentions

In general, respondents say that they are not ready to go back to Ukraine while the war is still ongoing.

Regarding her plans for the future, Olena, who is originally from Luhansk, and moved to Kyiv district in 2014 says that she is not ready to come back to Ukraine:

“We do not have a place to come back. Our house is destroyed. I do not think that the war will end soon. I do not know when I will feel safe in Ukraine again. If we stay here one more year, it will be difficult to come back. It means that we will not come back. My children start to integrate here. They are in the Swiss system. They are not involved in Ukrainian education.” (Olena)

Valentyna, whose son lives in Odesa and whose accommodation is not destroyed, says:

“It is difficult for me to answer now. I hope that everything will be okay and we will come back home.” (Valentyna)

Maria, whose husband is in Ukraine, says:

“It is a very complex question. On one hand, if I had a job here and could work on my

projects (writing children's books), I would stay here. We are here because I am really worried about my daughter. My husband says "I am happy that you are there and I am not worried about you". (Maria)

Overall, refugees claim that it is difficult for them to make plans for the future. But they add that there are some factors that may influence their decision. They include conditions of accommodation in their home country (whether it is destroyed or not); employment (the possibility to find a job in Ukraine or in Basel); the possibility to live together with the family (especially, with the husbands); the possibility to work on the projects they like.

DISCUSSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

As the forced migration of Ukrainians as the result of the Russo-Ukrainian war is a new phenomenon, there is a lack of research on it. Moreover, it is hard to predict the duration of this crisis as the war is ongoing.

It must be stressed that the circumstances, which Ukrainian refugees have, are unique in comparison to other refugees, which makes it hard to implement previous scientific knowledge in this field to the studies on Ukrainian refugees.

Taking into account these features, this research brings an important discussion about Ukrainian refugees and their future plans and reflections on integration in Basel. This case study shows the domains, which are challenging for the refugees and overall describes what Ukrainian refugees think about their future plans in Basel. This study only focuses on highlighting the attitudes and thoughts of the refugees on the domains of integration and future plans without exploring how to make the integration more successful.

Moreover, this research contributes to forced migration studies in general, and to the forced migration of Ukrainians, in particular.

Practically, this study can be used by government and international organizations and agencies, think tanks, volunteers, and policymakers, whose target audience is Ukrainian refugees.

CONCLUSION

The Ukrainian refugee crisis, thought to be one of the fastest-growing since WWII, started because of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on 24th February. Data shows that on January 31st, there were more than 4 million registered Ukrainian refugees in Europe (UNHCR, 2023).

As the war is still ongoing, the question of the integration of Ukrainian refugees in Basel becomes relevant. Thus, this study aims at answering such research questions:

- 1) What are the plans of Ukrainian refugees in Basel for the near future (till 2024)?
- 2) What are the reflections on the integration of Ukrainian refugees in Basel?

This exploratory research was conducted in 2022-2023 by using qualitative research methodology (semi-structured in-depth interviews). Overall, 10 interviews with women, from 18 to 60 years old, who have “S” status in Basel-City were conducted.

The theoretical framework is based on the domains of successful integration made up by Ager and Strang (2008).

Summing up the analysis of the data due to the standard qualitative thematic interpretation, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Making plans for the near future (till 2024) is a difficult question to answer for the respondents. They state they do not plan to come to Ukraine until the war ends and they express the desire to work in Basel. Despite not mentioning their intentions for the future, they underline the factors which may influence their decisions. They include the conditions of the accommodation in the home country, employment, the possibility to live together with the members of the nuclear family, and the possibility to work on the projects they like.
2. The most challenging domains of integration for Ukrainian refugees are language and employment. Respondents express an understanding of the importance of German language proficiency and show their readiness to study German. But they highlight some challenges, which prevent them from successfully acquiring language skills. They include methods of teaching, taking care of the children, and mental health problems.
3. Regarding employment, respondents emphasize that they would like to work but currently, they are putting their efforts into learning the language. Employment is a

complex and challenging question for Ukrainian refugees. While reflecting on this issue, they state some problems, which negatively influence employment: mental health problems; care work, which they cannot share with the other parents of the children; they are not ready to change the occupation they had in Ukraine.

4. The domains, which Ukrainian refugees evaluate in a good way and mention that in general, they do not have any problems with include housing, education, and social connections.
5. Overall, the experience of using health services is evaluated positively. But some respondents mention that there exists a difference in treatment approaches in Ukraine and Switzerland, which is frustrating for them.
6. Regarding safety and stability, respondents mention that in general they feel safe in Switzerland but they have some struggles with their previous experience of war and new experience of integration in the new society, which sometimes makes them feel not safe.

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Annex 1. Information about the respondents

<i>Name</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Marital status</i>	<i>Place of residence in Ukraine</i>	<i>Occupation in Ukraine</i>
Maria	34 years old	Married, one daughter (7 years old)	Kyiv	Architect, children's book writer
Anna	40 years old	Divorced, two daughters (8 and 9 years old)	Zarokpattia Oblast	Accountant
Nadia	48 years old	Married, two sons (13 and 15 years old)	Lviv	Civil servant
Valentyna	43 years old	Divorced, one son (21 years old)	Chornomorsk (Odesa)	Accountant
Olena	36 years old	Married, 3 children (8, 6, 4 years old)	Brovary	Teacher
Anastasia	30 years old	Married, one daughter (1,5 years)	Kharkiv	Lecturer at the university
Alla	55 years old	Married, one daughter, one grandchild	Chornomorsk (Odesa)	Port worker
Olga	35 years old	Married, one son (7 years old)	Odesa	Entrepreneur
Victoria	51 years old	Single, one daughter (4 years old)	Kyiv	Lecturer at the university
Kate	49 years old	Single, one daughter (23 years old)	Zaporizhzhia/ Kyiv	Worked at the insurance company

